

Appendix A. Data extraction form

Table A.1: Data extraction form

Extracted data type	No.	Data item name	Descriptions	Corresponding RQs
General information of the primary studies	D1	Authors	The authors of the papers.	
	D2	Year	The time when the papers are published.	
	D3	Publication venue	The venue in which the paper is published.	
Case metadata	D4	Case organization name	The name of the case organizations that practiced participatory reuse.	
	D5	Project name	The name of the project that practiced participatory reuse.	
	D6	The source	The source of the data, e.g., book, peer-reviewed papers, PhD thesis, videos.	
Case abstract	D7	Case summary	Short narrative description of the case	
Unit of analysis	D8	Unit of analysis	The description of the participatory reuse practice in the case organization.	
Case context	D9	Organizational context	Information related to the context, such as product information, development methodologies, and organizational information.	
Study data	D10	Reusable assets	The reusable assets that the case organization used in participatory reuse.	RQ1, RQ2
	D11	Roles and responsibilities	The roles and responsibilities that are defined in participatory reuse.	RQ1, RQ2
	D12	Communication and coordination	The soft collaboration and communication in participatory reuse, such as discussions, forums, and meetings. The tools used for collaborating and communicating participatory reuse, such as mailing lists and Jira.	RQ1, RQ2
	D13	Infrastructure	The tools and techniques that are used to develop, integrate, test, deploy and host reusable assets in participatory reuse.	RQ1, RQ2
	D14	Funding	The resource support for participatory reuse.	RQ1, RQ2
	D15	Organizational supports	The culture, policy and management roles in supporting participatory reuse.	RQ1, RQ2
	D16	Processes and practices	The processes and practices that detail the participatory reuse.	RQ1, RQ2

Appendix B. Description of participatory reuse taxonomy (v.1)

Figure B.1 presents the full version of the participatory reuse taxonomy (v.1), including both dimensions and elements. Below is a detailed description of the elements.

Reusable assets. They are the shared assets in participatory reuse. The results showed that the case organizations reported eight types of reusable assets, which are platforms, components, microservices, libraries, frameworks, design patterns, packages and web servers.

Roles and responsibilities. Clear roles and responsibilities help organizations understand who is responsible for which tasks in participatory reuse. The results show four main roles in participatory reuse: central team, support team, consumer teams, and steering group.

- The **central team** is the core team that is responsible for the development of the common reusable assets. The development responsibilities can be further categorized into six responsibility areas: design and scope, plans and roadmaps, architecture and development, test and code review, maintenance and updates, and management and administration.

Figure B.1: Participatory reuse taxonomy (v.1) with elements

- The **support team** is responsible for supporting the development, maintenance, and contribution of common reusable assets (category - technical support). It may also establish and promote the participatory reuse culture (category - culture support). Depending on the scale and adoption maturity of the participatory reuse, some organizations described the support tasks within the central team, while some established specific teams, such as anchor teams and culture teams, to handle these tasks.
- The **steering group** is responsible for the overall architecture, design and scope, and roadmap planning of common reusable assets and answering questions about common reusable assets, which includes representatives - usually architects, from both the consumer teams and the central team.
- **Consumer teams** are the (potential) consumers of the common reusable assets, which are mainly responsible for reusing and contributing to the development, maintenance, and review of common reusable assets. Consumer teams can also contribute to supporting tasks, such as mentoring new contributors.

Communication and coordination. Participatory reuse involves diverse stakeholders from different business units in an organization, necessitating the use of various communication and coordination channels. We classified communication and coordination into two forms: live and digital.

- The **live** ones are usually physically presented through discussions, meetings, and talks, which cover technical and coordination communication, as well as knowledge sharing. Technical communication often involves multiple stakeholders and requires in-depth discussions, which live sessions fit more. Coordination communication mainly includes work planning and progress monitoring. Live updates make coordination more efficient. Live sessions also involve knowledge sharing, particularly through training sessions and motivational talks. When delivered by a recognized figure within the organization, it can significantly boost practitioners' willingness to engage in participatory reuse.
- The **digital** ones are usually based on collaborating tools, especially for documenting or exchanging information. According to Lanubile et al. [1], we categorized the collaborating tools into four categories: Tracker, asynchronous tools, synchronous tools, and Web 2.0 applications.

Infrastructure. The reusable assets need basic infrastructure facilities for their storage, development, integration, and deployment that support participatory reuse. Based on the extracted data, we identified four infrastructure types: code repository, repository of the code repository, continuous integration and deployment, and other technical foundations.

- **Code repository** stores, manages, and tracks the source code for the reusable assets, along with documentation, configuration files, and other related assets. Code repositories often use version control systems like Git, which allow developers to collaborate, maintain a history of changes, track different versions, and easily revert to previous code status. GitHub, for example, is a popular platform for hosting code repositories.
- **Repository of the code repository** refers to internal portals that are centralized, secure, and designed to facilitate efficient access, management, and collaboration around code repositories within an organization. This portal provides developers and other relevant stakeholders with a comprehensive overview of all relevant details and resources related to the code repositories, such as repository metadata, analytics, and reporting.
- **Continuous integration and deployment of the common reusable assets** refers to the platform that enables the automation of integrating, testing, and releasing common reusable assets. Continuous integration ensures that changes from multiple contributors are regularly merged and validated, while continuous deployment automates the release of these validated assets to target environments. This approach enhances consistency, reduces integration overhead, and accelerates the delivery of reliable and reusable assets.
- **Other technical foundations** include the infrastructure that is not identified above.

Funding. Developing and contributing common reusable assets for organizational reuse takes additional costs. A clear funding strategy helps ensure the central team has enough resources to develop common reusable assets in participatory reuse. We identified two funding types in the included cases: distributed funding and central funding.

- **Distributed funding** refers to a decentralized model where funding is sourced from multiple consumer teams that reuse the developed common reusable assets from the central team.
- **Central funding** refers to a centralized model where funding is collected, managed, and allocated in one division, project, or organization.

Organizational support. Organizational support is essential to promote and sustain participatory reuse. We identified three categories based on the extracted data: culture, policy, and management support.

- **Culture** refers to the shared beliefs, values, practices, traditions, and behaviors that characterize participatory reuse in an organization. Within the element culture, the **motivation for adopting participatory reuse** stands for the reason developers believe it is worth adopting participatory reuse. **Incentives and rewards** are the encouragement that supports developers in engaging in participatory reuse. **Environment for participatory reuse** is the social norms and facilities that help sustain participatory reuse.
- **Policies** are the organizational rules or guidelines that the developers suggested or mandated to follow while practicing participatory reuse.
- **Management role** is important, which provides the backing, guidance, resources, and involvement to ensure the success of participatory reuse.

Processes and practices. Organizations applied different processes and practices to reinforce participatory reuse in the aforementioned dimensions. Based on the extracted data and previous categorization in different dimensions, we classify the processes and practices into ten areas: architecture and development, code review, maintenance, intellectual property rights, communication and coordination, culture, monitoring, plans and roadmaps, tools and infrastructures, and reuse and integration.

- **Architecture and development** contains the processes and practices used to improve the architecture and development of reusable assets.
- **Code review** contains the processes and practices for the review of pull requests (mainly contributions) to the reusable assets.
- **Maintenance** contains the practices used to maintain reusable assets, including quality assessment methods, problem-solving practices, ownership issues, and traceability.
- **Intellectual property rights** contains practices for the access and security measurement of the reusable asset.
- **Communication and coordination** contains practices used to facilitate the communication and coordination of participatory reuse.
- **Organizational support** contains the culture, common belief (e.g., transparency), and necessary training regarding participatory reuse.
- **Monitoring** contains practices that track the use of participatory reuse and the status of the reusable assets.
- **Plans and roadmaps** contains the practices that help address the work planning or roadmap conflicts between the central team and consumer teams.
- **Tools and infrastructures** contains practices that facilitate participatory reuse, such as automation.
- **Reuse and integration** contains practices followed to ensure the success of reuse and integration in participatory reuse.

Appendix C. Taxonomy expert evaluation questions

1. Conciseness:
 - Does the taxonomy include only the required number of dimensions and elements (i.e., no unnecessary or redundant dimensions) necessary to represent the participatory reuse effectively?
2. Robustness:
 - Are the dimensions of the taxonomy and elements within each dimension clearly distinct and distinguishable from each other?
 - Are the elements (within each dimension) closely related to each other?
3. Comprehensiveness:
 - Do the dimensions of the taxonomy capture all important aspects of participatory reuse? Are there any missing dimensions?
 - Do the elements within each dimension capture all aspects relevant to the respective dimensions? Are there any missing elements in any dimension of the taxonomy?
4. Explanatory:
 - Are the taxonomy dimensions, elements, and terms clearly described?

Appendix D. Detailed characterization of participatory reuse in the case organizations

Appendix D.1. Roles and responsibilities

Table D.2: Participatory reuse roles and responsibilities in organizations

Roles	Responsibilities area	Cases [references] and the reported responsibilities
Central team	Design and scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GlobalSoft [2, 3], Lucent [4], Google [5], Siemens [6] reported that the central team was responsible for identifying the commonality from consumer teams or legacy codes, scoping the common reusable assets, and deciding what new features should be included in the common reusable assets while ensuring the quality of the existing ones. - HP [7] reported that the central team members were responsible for leading the specification of the common reusable assets. In addition, IBM [8] reported that the project manager from the central team was responsible for approving the reusable assets proposals.
	Plans and roadmaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Siemens [6] reported that the central team was responsible for planning the backlog of common reusable assets.
	Architecture and development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GlobalSoft [2, 9, 3], Lucent [10, 4, 11, 12], HP (CDP) [13, 14, 7, 15], Ericsson [12, 16, 17], Google [18, 5], Siemens [6], Philips Healthcare [19, 20, 21, 22, 23] reported that the central team was responsible for developing common reusable assets. In addition, Lucent [11] and HP [7] also reported that the central team was responsible for developing the architecture of common reusable assets. - Lucent [12], HP [7], and Philips Healthcare [21] reported that the central team was responsible for documenting the common reusable assets, such as how they were being used across the organization. Moreover, HP [7] also reported that the central team was responsible for documenting the architecture of common reusable assets, including architectural guidelines, definitions, and architecture infrastructure documentation. - HP [7] and Ericsson [12, 16, 17] reported that the central team was responsible for standardizing the development rules of the common reusable assets, such as code style and test requirements.
	Test and code review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lucent [12] and Philips Healthcare [21] reported that the central team was responsible for testing common reusable assets. - For code review, PayPal [12, 24, 25] reported that the central team was responsible for reviewing all code submissions relevant to common reusable assets. Lucent [10, 4, 11, 12], Ericsson [12, 16, 17], Siemens [6] reported that the central team was responsible for reviewing the contributions from consumer teams. HP [7] also reported that the central team was responsible for reviewing the architecture of common reusable assets.
	Maintenance and updates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lucent [10, 4], Ericsson [12, 16, 17], Google [5], and Philips Healthcare [20, 22, 23] reported that the central team was responsible for maintaining common reusable assets. Lucent [11, 12] and HP [7] also reported that the central team was responsible for maintaining the architecture of common reusable assets. - Google [5] reported that the central team was responsible for updating consumers about the changes in common reusable assets. - GlobalSoft [2] and Philips Healthcare [21] reported that the steering group was responsible for addressing the questions from the mailing lists.
	Management and administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lucent [11, 26, 12], HP [7], Ericsson [12, 16, 17], Google [5], IBM [8] reported that the central team was responsible for managing planning and communication within the central team and between the central team and consumer teams. To detail it, Ericsson [12] and IBM [8] reported that the central team was responsible for managing roles around common reusable assets. Philips Research [21] reported that the central team was responsible for coordination and leadership for participatory reuse. - Lucent [11] and PayPal [12] reported that the central team was responsible for managing the process compliance. - Lucent [11] reported that the central team was responsible for managing tools used to define and track features.
Consumer teams	Reuse and integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Philips Healthcare [21] reported that the consumer teams were responsible for using the early version of common reusable assets to provide early feedback.
	Contribute to development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lucent [10, 4], Ericsson [12, 17], Europace AG [12], Google [5], S-Group Solution [27, 28], and Philips Healthcare [22, 23, 21] reported that the consumer teams were responsible for contributing to the development of common reusable assets.
	Contribute to maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Philips Healthcare [22, 23] reported that the consumer teams were responsible for maintaining the contributed part or changed part in common reusable assets.
	Contribute to code review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Google [5] reported that all developers were responsible for reviewing the code submission to identify potential reusable.

Table D.2 continued from previous page

Roles	Responsibilities area	Cases [references] and the reported responsibilities
		- Ericsson [16, 17] and S-Group Solution [28] reported that the consumer teams were responsible for contributing to the review of the contributions or the code submissions for reusable assets.
	Contribute to technical and cultural support	- For technical support, Ericsson [16, 17] reported that the consumer teams were responsible for contributing to the creation and participation in the discussion forms of common reusable assets. Philips Healthcare [19, 29] reported that the marketers in consumer teams were responsible for discussing the participatory reuse problem. Nokia [19] reported that the key users of the reusable assets serve as the contact person for users. - For cultural support, Europace AG [12] and Philips Healthcare [19, 29] reported that the consumer teams were responsible for contributing to the culture change. In addition, Ericsson [12, 17] reported that the consumer teams were responsible for contributing to mentoring the new contributors.
	Contribute to Q&A	- Ericsson [16, 17] reported that the consumer teams contribute to address questions from the communication channels.
Support team	Technical support	- GlobalSoft [2, 3] reported that the support team was responsible for standardizing development environments. In addition, GlobalSoft [2, 3] and Lucent [11] reported that the support team was responsible for supporting development and delivery environments. - Philips Healthcare [21] reported that the support team was responsible for testing support. Lucent [11, 12] reported that the support team was responsible for supporting the maintenance of common reusable assets and supporting consumers in using and maintaining common reusable assets. - Lucent [11, 12], and Ericsson [12, 16, 17] reported that the support team was responsible for supporting consumers in contributions. In addition, PayPal [12] reported that the support team also supported in establishing the contribution guidelines. - For infrastructure and tool support, Lucent [4, 11, 12] reported that the support team was responsible for maintaining the common reusable assets repository. HP [13, 14, 7] reported that the support team was responsible for supporting the collaboration infrastructure. - Ericsson [16, 17] reported that the support team was responsible for keeping track of the participatory reuse progress. Similarly, Lucent [11] reported that the support team was responsible for keeping track of the consumers' impacts on releases. - Ericsson [16] reported that the support team was responsible for updating the support in developing, reusing, and contributing.
	Non-technical support	- Lucent [11], HP [13, 14, 7, 15], Ericsson [12], Zalando [24, 25], Europace AG [12], Google [5] reported that the support team was responsible for enabling the culture change. To do so, Ericsson [16, 17], PayPal [25], and Zalando [25] reported that the support team was responsible for establishing the policy and guidelines for the participatory reuse ecosystem. HP [13, 14, 7, 15], Ericsson [12, 17], PayPal [12, 25], and Zalando [25] reported that the support team was responsible for participatory reuse training. Lucent [10, 4, 11, 12] reported that the support team was responsible for sharing/advertising common reusable assets. Google [5] reported that the support team was responsible for sharing reuse experiences and advice. - HP [13] reported that the support team was responsible for recognizing and rewarding consumers for collaboration.
Steering group	Design and scope	- Nokia [19] and Philips Healthcare [20, 21] reported that the steering group was responsible for identifying and scoping the common reusable assets. - HP [7], and Ericsson [16, 17, 12] reported that the steering group was responsible for driving and governing the principle, design rules, and guidelines related to the reusable assets architecture and maintenance.
	Architecture	- Ericsson [16, 17] reported that the steering group was responsible for determining the architecture direction of the common reusable assets.
	Plans and roadmaps	- GlobalSoft [9] reported that the steering group was responsible for planning the roadmap or backlog of the common reusable assets.
Others		- Nokia [19] reported that the IT department was responsible for maintaining the infrastructure. - Ericsson [16] reported that incompatible changes need to be reviewed both on the architecture and business levels without mentioning the specific roles. - Ericsson [17] and Google [5] reported that managers and technical leads were responsible for checking legal compliance without mentioning the detailed roles.

Table D.3: Participatory reuse communication and coordination activities in organizations

Communication and coordination type	Cases [references] and the reported communication and coordination means
Technical communication	- Discussions and meetings were mentioned for a variety of technical purposes by different organizations, i.e., discussions on the architecture of common reusable assets (GlobalSoft [9], Ericsson [12], S-Group Solutions [27], and Philips Healthcare [19, 29, 23, 21]), discussions on scoping and planning the roadmap of common reusable assets (Siemens [6], S-Group Solutions [27], and Philips Healthcare [19, 29]), discussions on consumers' change requests (Google [5]), discussion of contribution between producers and consumers (S-Group Solutions [27]), discussions on the contribution rules (PayPal [12]), and meetings to collect participatory reuse issues (PayPal [12]).
Coordination	- Meetings and discussions for coordination purposes were also mentioned by different organizations, i.e., development tasks synchronization meetings (Siemens [6]), monthly meetings with sponsoring executives about the participatory reuse update and asked for support (PayPal [12]), participatory reuse transformation overall planning meetings (PayPal [12]), and negotiation discussion between the consumer teams and the central team about the contribution type - monetary or developer resources (Lucent [12]).
Knowledge sharing	- To enable knowledge sharing, different live sessions were practiced in the organizations, i.e., communications to management-level and relevant stakeholders about participatory reuse knowledge (Lucent [12], PayPal [12], Ericsson [12], and Europace AG [12]), participatory reuse training sessions (PayPal [12] and Philips Healthcare [21]), talks for sharing participatory reuse experiences and works (Lucent [4] and Zalando [25]), and daily participatory reuse interactions to exchange experiences and knowledge - e.g., asking around for common reusable assets (Lucent [12], Google [5], and S-Group Solutions [27]).

Appendix D.3. Infrastructure

Table D.4: Participatory reuse infrastructure in organizations

Infrastructure type	Reported infrastructures	Cases [references] and the reported infrastructures
Technical infrastructure	Code repository	- Lucent [10, 4, 11], HP [30, 13], Ericsson [12], PayPal [12, 24], Zalando [24, 25], Google [18, 5], Europace AG [12], S-Group Solutions [27, 28], and Philips Healthcare [26, 22, 23] reported that the common reusable assets were stored in a central code repository.
	Reusable assets portal	- Lucent [10, 4, 11, 12], HP [30, 13, 14, 7], Ericsson [12, 16, 17], Zalando [24, 25], IBM [8], Nokia [19, 29, 31], Philips Healthcare [23] and Philips research [22, 23, 21, 26] reported that an internal portal [i.e., internal website (Lucent Technologies, Philips Healthcare), a web page named HP Labs Research Library (HP), marketplace portal (Ericsson), API portal (Zalando), GForge (IBM), iSource web portal (Nokia), an internal forge (Philips research)] was used for the information of the central code repository which includes but not limited to common reusable assets search, information (e.g., maturity stage, owners, contributors, consumers, access information) and tools (e.g., tracker, version control) about the reusable assets, instructions on how to use them, guidelines for publishing and contributing to reusable assets .
	Continuous integration and deployment of the common reusable assets	- Ericsson [16, 17] and S-Group Solutions [27, 28] used CI/CD pipelines for continuous integration and deployment. - Ericsson [17, 16] used Spinnaker ¹ to assemble the microservices into applications and orchestrate the pipelines, Helm ² to perform deployment and upgrades, and a DR checker to automate the review of the compliance of the development rules.
	Other technical foundations	- Ericsson [16, 17] reported they used Kubernetes ³ as a container orchestrator and Docker ⁴ as the cloud container for reusable assets.
Communication infrastructure	Knowledge sharing tools	- Philips Healthcare [19, 29, 23] reported using emails, FTP, CD, and the discussion group feature from the CollabNet tool for asynchronous communication. - GlobalSoft [2, 3], Google [5], Apache [12], and Philips Healthcare [26, 25, 19, 29, 23, 21] reported using mailing lists for asynchronous communication. HP [7, 14] also reported using emails for discussion. - Zalando [25] reported using NewsGeneral - a video-sharing service, IntoKnow Facebook, Jetlife (two internal social media tools), and a shared platform for asynchronous communication. - Europace AG [12] reported using blog, GitHub discussions, and Trello board for asynchronous communication.

¹<https://spinnaker.io/>

²<https://helm.sh/>

³<https://kubernetes.io/>

⁴<https://www.docker.com/>

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Infrastructure type	Reported infrastructures	Cases [references] and the reported infrastructures
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Google [5] and Philips Healthcare [19, 29] reported using Intranet for asynchronous communication. In addition, Google [5] reported using newsletters and user guides for asynchronous communication. - Europace AG [12] reported using Slack channel for synchronous communication. - S-Group Solutions [28] reported using Microsoft Teams and webhooks for synchronous communication. - Google [5] reported using Google+ for synchronous communication.
	Knowledge persistence tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GlobalSoft [2, 3], Europace AG [12], IBM [8], HP [7, 14], and Philips Healthcare [21] reported using issue tracker from Jira or GitHub to report and communicate problems. - Lucent [11] reported a request list web to track the requests from consumers and prioritize them. - GlobalSoft [2, 3], HP [14, 7], Europace AG [12], IBM [32, 8], S-Group Solutions [28], and Philips Healthcare [26, 25, 22, 23, 21] reported using Wiki, an information system to allow participatory reuse stakeholders to share participatory reuse knowledge. - Paypal [12, 25] reported using the GitHub repository for sharing participatory reuse knowledge, such as the name of the trusted committer and written conversation. Europace AG [12] reported that they used GitHub repository to log everything related to participatory reuse works. - Zalando [25] reported using DeveloperConsol to share the developer profiles. - Philips Healthcare [3] reported using Stylebase for Eclipse for sharing architectural knowledge.

Appendix D.4. Funding

Table D.5: Participatory reuse funding in organizations

Funding type	Cases [references] and the reported funding strategies
Distributed funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lucent [4, 11] reported that the lead consumer division funded the central team, and other consumer divisions contributed to the fund. It also reported that multiple consumer divisions collectively funded a support team [11]. - Nokia [19, 29] reported that consumer teams shared costs based on the number of active users. - The funding strategy reported in Philips Healthcare is relatively more comprehensive. In the early publications, they reported that consumer teams shared costs based on the licensing scheme or the annual turnover and the number of common reusable assets the consumer teams used [19, 29, 20, 23]. Contributors from the consumer teams pay the central team for the contribution support [20], and the consumer teams that have actively contributed can reduce their annual fee [20, 23]. In the later publication, they added that the central team also buys in the contributions from the consumer teams [21].
Central funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HP (CS) [30, 13, 14, 7] reported that the development of common reusable assets was centrally funded via a lab project. Moreover, HP (CDP) [7] reported the organization centrally funded the central team. - Ericsson [16, 17] reported that the central team that is responsible for the development and maintenance of common reusable assets (including the contributions from the consumer teams) was centrally funded by the organization.

Appendix D.5. Organizational support

Table D.6: Participatory reuse organizational support in organizations

Organizational support	Cases and the reported elements in culture/policy/management aspects
Culture - Motivations of participatory reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PayPal and Philips Healthcare reported the quantifiable gains [12, 24] and the knowledge gains [25] motivated them to adopt participatory reuse, respectively. GlobalSoft [9] also reported that the consumer teams need to see clear benefits from implementing participatory reuse. HP [15] reported they outlined the benefits of adopting participatory reuse in internal "tech reports". - Philips Research [33], IBM [8], and Ericsson [12] reported that changing the code in common reusable assets and finishing work quicker motivates them to adopt participatory reuse. - Lucent [26] reported that the fun in contribution motivated consumer teams to contribute to the common reusable assets.
Culture - Incentives and rewards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ericsson [16, 17] reported that they reward contributors with public notice for their contributions. Similarly, HP [30, 13] reported that they reward contributors through mail appraisal. - PayPal [12] and Europace AG [12] reported that they reward contributors with a role called trusted committer. Apache [12] also reported that they have guaranteed rewards for contributions, and they reward contributors with unexpired merit.

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Organizational support	<p>Cases and the reported elements in culture/policy/management aspects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PayPal [12] reported that suitable extrinsic rewards should be given to overcome reticence and kickstart collaborative work in participatory reuse. Google [18] also reported that they have global incentives for participatory reuse. - Apache [12] and Ericsson [12] reported that having equal votes between merit contributors and newcomers and celebrating cross-team collaboration success encourages participatory reuse. In addition, Philips Research [21, 33] reported that users' appreciation is also one of the incentives for contributing.
Culture - Environment for participatory reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Europace AG [12], Apache [12], and Philips Healthcare [24] reported having a transparent culture in participatory reuse. - PayPal [25] reported that improved infrastructure is vital for participatory reuse. - Google [5] reported having a direct communication culture in participatory reuse. - HP [13] reported having a supportive culture in participatory reuse. - GlobalSoft [9] reported the culture that the consumers should be willing to contribute.
Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lucent [12] reported that they have policies that developers should reuse reusable assets internally first rather than externally. In addition, Ericsson [17] reported that reusing certain assets is mandated to keep consistent user experiences. - Ericsson [16] reported that they set contribution targets for consumer teams. - Europace AG [12] reported they have established participatory reuse principles. Google [18, 5] also reported having mandate rules and measures for reuse.
Management role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lucent [11] reported that the management role should support the chief architect in scoping the reusable assets. - HP [15], Europace AG [12], Philips Healthcare [26, 23, 21], PayPal [12], and Lucent [12] reported that management roles should support changes due to participatory reuse, e.g., work process. - Ericsson [24], and Philips research [21, 26] reported that management roles should support acknowledging the contribution value from the consumers. - Nokia [19] reported that the management role should support decisions on tools and technology adoptions. - HP [13] reported that they established a comprehensive program for participatory reuse transition, including a capabilities review and training program to ensure the company is well prepared for implementing participatory reuse. It also includes a structure that ensures the ongoing behavioral migration towards participatory reuse. PayPal [12] reported that participatory reuse training differs in roles and can be classified into four categories: introduction to InnerSource, training on how to be a contributor and trusted committer, and training product managers on how to make process changes accordingly. They used a mass training period to onboard most engineers (all potential guest contributors), and the central team prepared different strategies to train for participatory reuse, such as slides, quizzes, multiple-choice, non-obvious answers, Q&A for training, and provided training sessions to as many people as possible. Nokia [19] also mentioned that the iSource service provides basic self-training material or buys training courses from third parties.
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PayPal [12, 25], Zalando [25], Google [5], S-Group Solutions [28], and Philips Healthcare [25] reported that they tracked the collaboration situation among teams in participatory reuse. The following metrics are developed by different companies, such as lines of code for reusable assets divided by lines of code for the application. - Ericsson [16, 17] reported that they used compliance with the development rules to classify the maturity of the common reusable assets to see how commercially ready they are. In addition, they also used the number of reuses to classify the reusability of the reusable assets. The higher staircase means that many applications have successfully reused the reusable assets. Google [5] also reported that they evaluate the maturity of the reused artifacts and the degree of entangledness between the own code and the reused artifacts. - Ericsson [12] also tracks the use of the reusable assets.

Appendix D.6. Processes and practices

Table D.7: Processes and practices that reinforce the participatory reuse

Processes and practices areas	Cases [references] and the reported processes and practices
Architecture and development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GlobalSoft [9, 2, 3] reported that the central team performed dynamic scoping - scrutinizing the new software product and identifying the parts that could be adopted into the common reusable assets platform. - Siemens [6] reported that they introduced a plug-in architecture to help reduce the detailed scoping and planning, avoid the need for approvals from the central team, and enable the independent releases of specific functionality. They also used feature slicing to reduce the dependencies among components, enable delivering components corresponding to the delivered features only, and reduce the reliance on integration and system tests. In addition, at the start of each version, teams will have an architecture corridor - teams were allotted time to move common functionality to the platform or the reuse layers in architecture to optimize variability and improve reuse.

Table D.7 continued from previous page

Processes and practices areas	Cases [references] and the reported processes and practices
	<p>- HP [7] reported an architecture development process: a small group of developers from the central team developed the common reusable assets architecture, including documenting its guidelines and infrastructure. Once developed, the entire central team reviews the architecture. In addition, the Sirius team with the OWEN project used a common architecture that can be split into manageable pieces. To avoid disconnection from the architectural principles and facilitate collaborative development on a larger scale, the interconnected central team should be responsible for delegating the components across the teams.</p> <p>- Google [5] reported a process for including new reusable assets. The organization has a dedicated place called an incubator where developers can place potential reusable assets. The usage of the potential reusable assets will be monitored over time. If the potential reusable asset obtains sufficient usage, the central team will invest in improving its reusability and maturity and incorporate it into the library.</p> <p>- PayPal [12], HP [7], and Ericsson [12] reported that their documentation includes objectives, processes and methods of creating and contributing to the common reusable assets, the relationship and responsibilities of both the central team (receiving contributions) and consumer teams (contributing), e.g., the “30 days after deploy” warranty that the guest contributor must honor.</p> <p>- Ericsson [16, 17] reported that they established some ground development rules to avoid inconsistent behaviors in the integration, reuse, and contribution of the common reusable assets.</p> <p>- GlobalSoft [2, 9, 3], Lucent [10, 4, 12], Siemens [6] and Philips Healthcare [26, 20, 23, 21] reported collaborative development - the developers from the central team and consumer teams work together to develop a new reusable asset or enriching the existing ones, to help to conform the architecture of the common reusable assets and meanwhile meets the consumers’ needs.</p>
Design and scope	<p>- Apache [12] reported that they used voting to reach a consensus on what feature to add or what patches and contributions to accept. The voting process starts when someone proposes something and asks for a vote. If someone, even one person, votes against a point, they will step back and continue the discussion. The vote will be closed when there is no disagreement.</p> <p>- Google [5] reported that reviewing the code changes helps them identify the missed reuse opportunities.</p>
Plans and roadmaps	<p>- Ericsson [16] reported that the central teams collected all requirements and divided them into two backlogs depending on their priorities: active backlog keeps the prioritized requirements that will be implemented in the next 12 months, while not active backlog keeps the low prioritized requirements that will not be implemented in the next 12 months as future candidates. According to the backlogs, the consumer teams can plan whether to wait for the central team to implement the feature or contribute.</p> <p>- Philips Research [26] reported that the developers will work intensively on the common reusable assets when a new feature or improvement is necessary and time is available.</p>
Test and Code review	<p>- Ericsson, Zalando, and Lucent particularly emphasized the importance of the code review for the reusable assets’ submissions (mainly the contributions). Ericsson [12] reported that all contributions should be rigorously reviewed before committing to the repository to ensure high quality, even the parts written by the Trusted Committers. Zalando [25] reported business processes used for peer review and investigating problem reports. For example, for compliance reasons, the code committed to reusable code should be reviewed by multiple developers, and the reviewers should provide structured comments of approval when merging code. Zalando also has an “API first” principle to capture the internal data components. The capture of reusable infrastructure components also required standardized approaches to capturing data and business process components to maintain cohesion and quality. Lucent [4] reported that since consumer teams’ expectations and habits may misaligned from the central team, a special review process was established for the contributions from consumer teams. The contribution review process includes mandatory review, tracking all comments in reviews, and re-reviewing the modified code.</p> <p>- To avoid inconsistent behaviors and implementations from consumers, it is important to define and document rules or principles for developing or contributing reusable assets. Ericsson [16] reported that they automated the implementation and compliance review of development rules to improve the aforementioned point.</p> <p>- Siemens [6] reported that they used automated manual tests to shorten the time required for integration testing.</p>
Maintenance	<p>- Ericsson [17] reported a deprecation period for backward incompatibility. When common reusable assets face backward incompatibility issues in changes, a deprecation of the changes will be registered. The deprecation will go through an architecture review and a business review before being approved, and the consumer teams have the opportunity to not approve it. Depending on the consumers’ needs, the deprecation period varies.</p>

Table D.7 continued from previous page

Processes and practices areas	Cases [references] and the reported processes and practices
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Google [5] reported constructive and analytical quality assessment methods, including serious review cycles, patterns and guidelines, maturity level, and solid testing infrastructure. It [5] also reported that when developers use reusable assets from each other, the traceability of the original location should be added in case of bugs and need for clarification. - GlobalSoft [2], Lucent [4, 12], and Philips Healthcare [22] reported that the central team can take back ownership of the local changes that the consumer teams made to common reusable assets. As such, the consumer teams will be free from maintaining the changed common reusable assets, and the central team can gain from the domain experts' views. - Europace AG [12] reported that to facilitate knowledge sharing, it is important to improve the traceability between issues, discussions, and their corresponding commits. - S-Group Solutions [27] reported that a new version number is assigned to the revised reusable assets to trace the changes and their original form. - Siemens [6] reported that they established a predefined defect threshold, and instituted a process whereby, upon exceeding this limit, all feature development activities are temporarily stopped, and actions are taken to reduce the defect count to the defined threshold before resuming normal feature development.
Intellectual property rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HP [7] and Google [5] reported that access to the common reusable assets should be specified to protect intellectual property rights. In addition, HP [7] also reported that the developers were reminded to take critical security measurements to protect intellectual property rights.
Communication and coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The communication infrastructure in Table D.4 shows that companies established the channels and forums for communication. - PayPal [12] reported they collected the written conversation between the contributors and the trusted committer to reduce the time mentoring the subsequent contributors and identify what should be formally documented. Similarly, HP [7] also reported that the discussion, solutions, and ideas were in written form with the code to facilitate knowledge sharing. - HP [7] reported that the consumer teams selected some team members as designated communicators responsible for particular issues. These designated communicators collect the relevant issues and questions and form them into one focused message daily, acting as an issue filter to facilitate communication. - Philips Research [26] and Apache [12] reported that announcing the preliminary work-in-progress or the work intention on the mailing list encourages work collaboration and gains early feedback. - Philips Research [26, 21] reported that the problem reports from consumers will be investigated immediately to solve the issues quicker and gain consumers' confidence in the quality of the common reusable assets.
Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HP [13] reported that they established a comprehensive program for participatory reuse transition, including a capabilities review and training program to ensure the company is well prepared for implementing participatory reuse. It also includes a structure that ensures the ongoing behavioral migration towards participatory reuse. - HP [7] also reported that they documented the success story of participatory reuse and shared the story company-wide to make employees within the company familiar with it and, in this way, inscribe it as a pattern for future development. - HP [14] reported that the common reusable assets should be transparent to everyone inside the organization - by default, the central team gives read access to common reusable assets to every member of the organization. - Europace AG [12] also mentioned the mechanism they used for written access. They grant written access in a meritocratic way: Contributors have to earn the trust of the reusable assets' maintainers to get written access to the repository and become the trusted committers of the reusable assets. As such, these contributors will be publicly recognized and will be responsible for future development. - Europace AG [12] reported a practice that allows people with relevant experiences to participate in the internal InnerSource pattern documentation. As such, allowing everyone to participate in the content creation process and seeing the results published externally gives credit to contributors and increases the motivation, engagement, and participation of those involved. Europace AG [12] reported a series of efforts to develop a common internal understanding of InnerSource: first, develop a concise set of six principles of InnerSource at Europace AG. Then, share and announce the results in the Slack channel and GitHub and reach out to individuals to invite everyone to give feedback, ask questions, and make changes. In the end, a final message was sent to everyone for the final review and consensus. - Europace AG [12] reported that they hired experienced open-source people to mentor participatory reuse, which helped them understand the reasons or benefits behind certain participatory reuse practices. - PayPal [12] reported that assessing the suitability of adopting participatory reuse (understanding the participatory reuse motivation) before adopting is important. - Ericsson [17, 34] reported that it is essential to define clear guidelines for integration, reuse, and contribution to promote consistency across teams.

Table D.7 continued from previous page

Processes and practices areas	Cases [references] and the reported processes and practices
Tools and infrastructure	<p>HP [7] reported that they give newcomers access to participatory reuse infrastructure and knowledge base, including norms and development guidelines.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zalando [25] reported that they used tools to automate feature branching and instant messaging when reviewing the code commit of reusable assets. - Europace AG [12] reported that they reused the communication tools already available for communication in participatory reuse.
Release, reuse, and integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Siemens [6] reported that they used more frequent releases to deliver new functionality quickly. - GlobalSoft [2, 3] reported that once the consumer teams use the common reusable assets from the central team, they should keep updated with the latest version. This will reduce the integration effort and avoid revisions when switching from one version to another. - Philips Healthcare [22] reported that the consumer teams were provided with three options for using reusable assets. They can reuse them verbatim, contribute to the reusable assets, or work with producers to develop or improve them. They [23] also added that to engage the consumer teams early in the development of common reusable assets, the central team labeled the version status for common reusable assets. There are three labels: Works-In-Progress are the tested versions of the software that are updated bimonthly. Snapshots are low-tested versions of the software and are updated biweekly. Bleeding Edge is an untested version of the software that is instantaneously accessible. - GlobalSoft [2, 3] reported that when the consumer teams that use the reusable assets miss functions shortly before the product release and the central team is not able to deliver the needed function in time, the consumer teams can be flexible in making local changes to the common reusable asset and building the products.

Appendix E. Checklist

Reusable assets:

Which of the following assets do you reuse in your participatory reuse practices?

Code related reusable assets:

1. Platforms (GlobalSoft, Lucent, Ericsson, Siemens, Philips Healthcare, Zalando) Yes No Want to have
2. Components (PayPal, Google, Philips Healthcare, Philips Research) Yes No Want to have
3. Microservices (Ericsson, Zalando, Europace AG, S-Group Solutions) Yes No Want to have
4. Libraries (Lucent, Google) Yes No Want to have
5. Frameworks (HP, Google) Yes No Want to have
6. Design patterns (Google) Yes No Want to have
7. Packages (S-Group Solutions) Yes No Want to have
8. Web servers (Apache) Yes No Want to have

Non-code related reusable assets:

1. Documentations (Siemens)

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Comments:

Roles and responsibilities

Do you have a central team responsible for developing and maintaining reusable assets? Yes No Want to have

If yes, which of the following responsibilities does the central team handle?

Design and scope:

1. Scope the reusable assets (GlobalSoft, Lucent, Google, Siemens) Yes No Want to have
2. Lead the specification and approve the contribution proposal of reusable assets (HP, IBM) Yes No Want to have

Plans and roadmaps:

1. Plan the backlog of reusable assets (Siemens) Yes No Want to have

Architecture and development:

1. Architect and develop reusable assets (GlobalSoft, Lucent, HP, Ericsson, Google, Siemens, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
2. Manage documentation of reusable assets, such as architecture documentation (Lucent, HP, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have

3. Establish the contribution rules (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Test and code review:

1. Test reusable assets (Lucent, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
2. Review and approve the pull requests or code commits of reusable assets (PayPal, Lucent, Ericsson, Siemens, HP) Yes No Want to have

Maintenance and updates:

1. Maintain the reusable assets (Lucent, Ericsson, Google, Philips Healthcare, HP) Yes No Want to have
2. Update consumers about the changes in reusable assets (Google) Yes No Want to have
3. Address Q&A in communication channels (GlobalSoft, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have

Governance and administrative management of the participatory reuse:

1. Manage planning, coordination, and communication among stakeholders to lead participatory reuse (Lucent, HP, Ericsson, Google, IBM, PayPal, Philips Research) Yes No Want to have
2. Manage tools used to define and track features (Lucent) Yes No Want to have

Do consumer teams contribute to the reusable assets that are managed by the central team? Yes No Want to have

If yes, which of the following responsibilities do the consumer teams handle?

Use and integration:

1. Provide feedback on the reusable assets (Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have

Contributions:

1. Provide feature contributions (Lucent, Ericsson, Europace AG, Google, S-Group Solution, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
2. Provide bug fixing or performance contributions (Google, Ericsson, S-Group Solutions) Yes No Want to have
3. Contribute to the review of the contributions (Ericsson, Philips Healthcare, Europace AG, Nokia) Yes No Want to have
4. Contribute to onboarding new comers (Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
5. Contribute to address Q&A in communication channels (GlobalSoft, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have

Do you have a support team responsible for supporting the stakeholders in developing and maintaining reusable assets and sustaining participatory reuse? Yes No Want to have

If yes, which of the following responsibilities does the support team handle?

If no, but you still have support-related responsibilities, which of the following does your company apply?

Technical support:

1. Support in using, testing, contributing, and maintaining reusable assets (Lucent, Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
2. Maintain the reusable assets portal, such as the marketplace (Lucent, HP) Yes No Want to have
3. Keep track of the participatory reuse progress (Ericsson, Lucent) Yes No Want to have
4. Standardize and support the development environments (GlobalSoft, Lucent) Yes No Want to have
5. Support in establishing the contribution rules (PayPal) Yes No Want to have
6. Update the support in developing, reusing, and contributing to reusable assets (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Non-technical support:

1. Establish training for participatory reuse (HP, Ericsson, PayPal, Zalando) Yes No Want to have
2. Enable the participatory reuse transition (Lucent, HP, Ericsson, Zalando, Europace AG, Google) Yes No Want to have
3. Establish policy and guidelines for participatory reuse (Ericsson, PayPal, Zalando) Yes No Want to have
4. Create awareness of the resource within the company (Lucent) Yes No Want to have
5. Recognize and reward consumers for collaboration (HP) Yes No Want to have

Do you have a steering group responsible for collaborative development and maintenance of reusable assets between the central team and consumer teams? Yes No Want to have

If yes, which of the following responsibilities does the steering group handle?

Collective design of reusable assets:

1. Collectively identify and scope the reusable assets (Nokia, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have

2. Drive and govern the principle, design rules, and guidelines related to the reusable assets architecture and maintenance (HP, Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Collective determination of architecture direction:

1. Collectively determine the reusable assets' architecture direction (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Collective plans and roadmaps:

1. Collectively plan the roadmap or backlog of reusable assets (GlobalSoft) Yes No Want to have

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Comments:

Communication and coordination activities

To support participatory reuse, communication and coordination are essential. There are three main types of such activities. Which of the following activities does your company apply?

Technical communication activities:

1. Have discussions on the architecture of reusable assets among architects or tech leads from the central team and consumer teams (GlobalSoft, Ericsson, S-Group Solutions, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
2. Have discussions on scoping and planning the roadmap of reusable assets among architects, tech leads, project managers, and product owners from the central team and consumer teams (Siemens, S-Group Solutions, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
3. Have discussions on consumers' change requests between the owner of the reusable assets and the consumers who made the change requests (Google) Yes No Want to have
4. Have discussions to align the needs and understand the contribution requirements between the reusable asset's owner and the consumer (S-Group Solutions) Yes No Want to have
5. Have discussions on the development of contribution rules among key executives, managers, and developers (PayPal) Yes No Want to have
6. Have meetings to collect participatory reuse issues between the support team and team leads from consumer teams (PayPal) Yes No Want to have

Coordination activities:

1. Establish meetings for synchronizing development tasks among scrum masters from different teams (Siemens) Yes No Want to have
2. Have meetings between the support team and sponsoring executives about the participatory reuse progress and ask for advice or support on specific issues (PayPal) Yes No Want to have
3. Have meetings for planning participatory reuse transformation among CTO, relevant engineering executives, senior managers and product owners, and the support team (PayPal) Yes No Want to have
4. Have contribution resource negotiation meetings between the consumer teams and the central team (Lucent) Yes No Want to have

Knowledge sharing activities:

1. Conduct sessions to increase the understanding of participatory reuse benefits among engineers and management level (Lucent, PayPal, Ericsson, Europace AG) Yes No Want to have
2. Have participatory reuse training sessions between the central team or support team and consumer teams (PayPal, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
3. Conduct sessions to increase the awareness of participatory reuse between stakeholders (Lucent, Zalando, Google, S-Group Solutions) Yes No Want to have

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Comments:

Infrastructure

To facilitate the sharing and communication of reusable assets, it is important to have the right infrastructure in place. Which of the following does your company use?

Technical infrastructure:

1. Code repository (Lucent, HP, Ericsson, PayPal, Zalando, Google, Europace AG, S-Group Solutions, Philips Health-care) Yes No Want to have
2. Reusable assets portal (Lucent, Philips Healthcare, HP, Ericsson, Zalando, IBM, Nokia, Philips Re-

search) Yes No Want to have

3. CI/CD of reusable assets: CI/CD pipelines (Ericsson, S-Group Solutions) Yes No Want to have

4. Other technical foundations:

- (a) Kubernetes (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
- (b) Docker (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Communication infrastructure:

1. Knowledge sharing tools
 - (a) Mailing lists (GlobalSoft, Google, Apache, Philips Healthcare, HP) Yes No Want to have
 - (b) Emails, FTP, CD, discussion group feature from CollabNet (Philips Healthcare, HP) Yes No Want to have
 - (c) A shared platform for discussion, Intranet (Zalando, Google, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
 - (d) Blog, GitHub discussions, Trello board (Europace AG) Yes No Want to have
 - (e) Newsletter and user guides (Google) Yes No Want to have
 - (f) Slack, Microsoft Teams and webhooks, Google+ (Europace AG, S-Group Solutions, Google) Yes No Want to have
2. Knowledge persistence tools
 - (a) Issue tracker, e.g., JIRA (GlobalSoft, Europace AG, IBM, Philips Healthcare, HP, Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
 - (b) A website that collects the requests from consumers (Lucent) Yes No Want to have
 - (c) Wiki (GlobalSoft, HP, Europace AG, IBM, S-Group Solutions, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
 - (d) GitHub repository (PayPal, Europace AG) Yes No Want to have
 - (e) A tool used to share developer profiles (Zalando) Yes No Want to have
 - (f) Stylebase for Eclips (Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have

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Comments:

Funding

Funding the development and maintenance of reusable assets is essential for enabling participatory reuse, particularly to support asset contributions.

Which of the following funding strategies does your company use for the development and maintenance of reusable assets?

1. Use distributed funding (Lucent, Nokia, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
2. Use central funding (HP, Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Which of the following funding strategies does your company have for the contribution of the reusable assets?

1. Use distributed funding (Lucent, Nokia, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
2. Use central funding (HP, Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

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Comments:

Organizational support

Within an organization, participatory reuse cannot flourish without strong organizational support. Which of the following organizational supports does your company have to support participatory reuse?

Culture for participatory reuse:

1. Motivation for adopting participatory reuse
 - (a) Improve the work efficiency (Philips Research, IBM, Ericsson, PayPal, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
 - (b) Have ability to boost the skill and profile through multi-disciplinary learning (Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
 - (c) Fun in contributing to reusable assets (Lucent) Yes No Want to have
2. Incentives and rewards for recognizing contributions
 - (a) Publicly appreciate the contributions, such as through mailing appraisal and announcing the lists of top contributors in intranet (Ericsson, HP) Yes No Want to have
 - (b) Appoint frequent contributors a trusted committer role (PayPal, Europace AG) Yes No Want to have

- (c) Treat newcomers and marginal participants equal to the existing contributors of reusable assets (Apache) Yes No Want to have
- (d) Celebrate the cross-team collaboration success (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
- (e) Appreciate the contributions from other consumers (Philips Research) Yes No Want to have
- 3. Open environment for participatory reuse
 - (a) Have an open and transparent culture in participatory reuse, including sharing and communicating the reusable assets, relevant material, and information. (Europace AG, Apache, Philips Healthcare, Google) Yes No Want to have
 - (b) Provide a strong technical foundation to support sharing and contributing to reusable assets (PayPal) Yes No Want to have
 - (c) Establish an organizational-wide program to support participatory reuse transition (HP) Yes No Want to have
 - (d) Reduce “not invented here” syndrome (GlobalSoft) Yes No Want to have

Reuse policies and principles:

- 1. Reuse internally first rather than externally (Lucent) Yes No Want to have
- 2. Mandate to reuse certain assets for a consistent user experience (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
- 3. Set contribution targets for consumer teams (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
- 4. Establish participatory reuse principles, such as make everything open, transparent, and findable, encourage contributions over feature requests, and favor written over verbal communication. (Europace AG) Yes No Want to have

Management backing for participatory reuse:

- 1. Support and motivate individuals and teams in engaging in participatory reuse, such as acknowledging the consumers’ contribution value and making decisions on tools and technology adoptions (HP, Europace AG, Philips Healthcare, PayPal, Lucent, Ericsson, Nokia, Lucent) Yes No Want to have
- 2. Support and establish training to onboard newcomers for participatory reuse (PayPal, Nokia) Yes No Want to have

Measurement for participatory reuse:

- 1. Use metrics to track participatory reuse cases, such as number of contributions (PayPal, Zalando, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
- 2. Use metrics to label the quality of the reusable assets, such as maturity level and reusability staircase (Ericsson, Google) Yes No Want to have
- 3. Track the use of reusable assets, such as reuse rate, number of users for reusable assets (Ericsson, Google, S-Group Solutions) Yes No Want to have

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Comments:

Processes and practices

In addition to the elements mentioned above, detailed processes and practices are needed to support participatory reuse. Which of the following processes and practices does your organization apply?

Processes and practices for developing and architecting reusable assets:

- 1. Encourage collaborative development of reusable assets between the central and consumer teams (GlobalSoft, Lucent, Siemens, Philips Healthcare, Zalando) Yes No Want to have
- 2. Document the objectives and methods of the participatory reuse projects, which helps remind the teams about the intention and facilitates participatory reuse communication, such as documenting the workflows of making a contribution. (HP, Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
- 3. Design or adopt extendable architecture solutions with low dependencies, such as use a plug-in architecture and feature slicing (Siemens) Yes No Want to have
- 4. Develop and document reusable asset architecture within a small, focused team, then conduct reviews with the full producer team to ensure its feasibility (HP) Yes No Want to have
- 5. Manage potential reusable components through an incubator process, where engineers submit reusable asset candidates. Their usage will be monitored, and when the candidates demonstrate sufficient adoption, they will be systematically enhanced and progressed through maturity stages before being incorporated into the official reusable assets portal. (Google) Yes No Want to have
- 6. Support the implementation of the general constraints and requirements of reusable assets through au-

tomation (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

7. Having a centrally funded team to help central teams with features that are not very complex but still have high value when the central teams are tight with their development bandwidth, such as implementing for fixing general design constraints or requirements. (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Processes and practices for designing and scoping reusable assets:

1. Make decisions on what features to add and contributions to accept in reusable assets through consensus, using votes to identify concerns and prompting discussion whenever objections arise (Apache) Yes No Want to have
2. Conduct code change reviews to identify missed reuse opportunities, enabling developers to revise their implementations and thereby maximize the extent of component reuse (Google) Yes No Want to have
3. Establish a process of proposing a new reusable assets: propose a new reusable assets, identify its use cases and stakeholders, conduct external and internal analysis to see if alternatives exist, perform criticality and capability assessment on the proposed reusable assets, document all the above information for review, archive all the information when the proposed reusable asset is approved. (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
4. Establish a structured contribution flow to classify the types of contributions and assign them to the appropriate stakeholder groups for review. (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Processes and practices for creating and updating plans and roadmaps:

1. Organize and share backlog in a way that the prioritization is clear to the consumers (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
2. Work on reusable assets opportunistically when needs arise and resources permit, ensuring incremental progress without blocking their own development tasks (Philips Research) Yes No Want to have
3. Digitalizing the plans and roadmaps for self-service and automation, such as digitalizing the requirement handling through feature and product tracker, automating aggregation of timelines and commitment status over multiple main requirements in a reusable asset. (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Processes and practices for testing and code review:

1. Have a standardized code review process for reusable assets, including the commits and pull requests from outside the team (Lucent, Zalando, Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
2. Automate the testing of the general constraints or requirements of the reusable assets, e.g., security or other compliance related requirements (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
3. Use automated tests to shorten the time required for integration testing (Siemens) Yes No Want to have

Processes and practices for maintaining reusable assets:

1. Have a deprecation process whereby incompatible changes were registered, reviewed architecturally and commercially, and subject to consumer approval to address backward incompatibility. (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have
2. Use constructive and analytical quality assessment methods to ensure the quality of reusable assets, such as serious review cycles, patterns and guidelines, maturity level, and solid testing infrastructure. (Google) Yes No Want to have
3. Ensure the traceability of the reusable assets, such as the original reusable assets location, the connection among issues, discussions, and commits (Google, Europace AG) Yes No Want to have
4. Have proper version control when new releases are made (S-Group Solutions) Yes No Want to have
5. Establish a defect threshold beyond which the feature development is paused until the defect count is below the threshold (Siemens) Yes No Want to have
6. Take back ownership of the local changes from the consumer teams (GlobalSoft, Lucent, Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
7. Have a grace period to allow the central team adapt the reusable assets to the newly established general constraints or requirements. (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Processes and practices for managing intellectual property rights:

1. Ensure the critical security measurements (HP) Yes No Want to have
2. Define clear access control rules, e.g., who can view or make changes to the reusable assets (HP, Google) Yes No Want to have

Processes and practices for communicating and coordinating across teams:

1. Establish the channels and forums for communication (GlobalSoft, Philips Healthcare, Zalando, Google, Europace AG, S-Group Solutions) Yes No Want to have

2. Appoint a designated communicator's role who is responsible for collecting and filtering the issues and questions into one focused message a day (HP) Yes No Want to have
3. Document the information around the reusable assets, e.g., conversation between contributors and trusted committers, and the discussions, solutions, and ideas about common reusable assets (PayPal, HP) Yes No Want to have
4. Respond to the consumers' problem reports within a specified time frame (Philips Research) Yes No Want to have
5. Announce the intention of working on a feature to gain early feedback (Philips Research, Apache) Yes No Want to have
6. Establish an interconnected central team to manage the large amount of knowledge that has to be communicated and internalized by the entire central team. No Want to have

Processes and practices for shaping and fostering culture:

1. Establish participatory reuse transition program, including review of participatory reuse capability and have the training program (HP) Yes No Want to have
2. Be transparent and have read-access for everyone to the shared reusable assets (HP) Yes No Want to have
3. Document success stories of participatory reuse (HP) Yes No Want to have
4. Grant written access in a meritocratic way: contributors have to earn the trust from the maintainers of the reusable assets to be able to get the write access to the repository and become the trusted committers of the reusable assets. (Europace AG) Yes No Want to have
5. Hire open source experienced people as participatory reuse mentors (Europace AG) Yes No Want to have
6. Understand the motivation for implementing participatory reuse before the teams or participants change to the participatory reuse process (PayPal) Yes No Want to have
7. Introduce formal governance early regarding participatory reuse, namely the structures, processes, and rules used to oversee and coordinate the initiative (Zalando) Yes No Want to have
8. Include all employees to participate in documenting participatory reuse principles and patterns (Europace AG) Yes No Want to have
9. Define clear guidelines for integration, reuse, and contribution to promote consistency across teams (Ericsson) Yes No Want to have

Processes and practices for establishing and managing tools and infrastructures:

1. Grant newcomers access to participatory reuse infrastructure and knowledge (HP) Yes No Want to have
2. Automate feature branching (e.g., use a tool or script to automatically create a corresponding Git branch following a naming convention when an issue is logged in Jira) and instant messaging (e.g., automated notifications when a pull request passes or fails, and alerts when new feature branches are created, code reviews are needed, or builds are complete) for participatory reuse (Zalando) Yes No Want to have
3. Use existing tools and infrastructure for participatory reuse rather than introduce new tools to the company (Europace AG) Yes No Want to have

Processes and practices for releasing, using, and integrating reusable assets:

1. Have more frequent releases to deliver new features quicker (Siemens) Yes No Want to have
2. Follow the latest version of the reusable assets (GlobalSoft) Yes No Want to have
3. Allow consumers to make local changes when close to product release (GlobalSoft) Yes No Want to have
4. Provide optional use of reusable assets, namely, reuse in verbatim, contribute to the reusable assets, or choose to work together with the central team to develop or improve the reusable assets. (Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have
5. Label the testing status of reusable asset versions (e.g., Works-In-Progress – tested, updated bimonthly; Snapshots – low-tested, updated biweekly; Bleeding Edge – untested, instantly accessible) and encourage consumers to use these early versions and provide feedback to improve quality. (Philips Healthcare) Yes No Want to have

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 Comments:

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